

A Note on the Use of Dimercaptothiobiazole as an Analytical Reagent.

BY JAGANNATH GUPTA.

has been found to be a very convenient reagent for the estimation of copper, lead and bismuth, and for their separation from the metals of the 11 A and the rest of the analytical groups (As, Sb, Sn, Mo, Fe, Zn, etc.). The substance serves also as a very sensitive micro-reagent for Cu and Bi. This work was completed in this laboratory by the end of December, 1933, under the guidance and suggestion of Prof. P. R. Ray and is now ready for submission as a part of my thesis for the ensuing M.Sc. examination in July.

In the meantime a paper by Dubsy and Okâc on "Qualitativer Nachweis des Wismuts mit schwefelhaltigen organischen Reagenzien—1. Nachweis mit Dimercaptothio-diazol" has appeared in the *Z. anal. Chem.*, **96**, (1934), 267. As our work cannot be published before my examination is over, it is necessary that a short note should now be communicated, though not with any intention of claiming priority so far as the reaction for Bi is concerned, but simply as a justification of our independent work in connection with Bi and as a reservation of our right with reference to Cu and Pb.

Copper has been separated in dilute acid solution from Zn, Mn, Ni, Co, Mo, Wo and Fe (in the ferrous state by treatment with SO₂), from As and Sn⁴⁺ in tartaric acid solution, and from Sn and Sb in the presence of sodium fluoride. Lead has been separated from Sn⁴⁺ in presence of tartaric acid, and from As, Sb and Sn in presence of tartaric acid and sodium fluoride. A similar separation has also been effected in the case of bismuth.

REVIEW

Essai sur la Chimie Comparée—Les corps simples—by Dr. I. N. Longinescu, Paris:. Published by Les Presses Universitaires de France 1932.

The author considers that in the study of inorganic chemistry insufficient attention has been paid to the relations among the members of the groups of the periodic system and hence attempts to fill up the deficiency. Undoubtedly the comparative treatment is advantageous and this small treatise may be looked upon as a good supplement to the existing works. Ephraim's *Anorganische Chemie* is planned on the same line.

Prof. Longinescu's second volume dealing with the binary compounds based on the same principle is awaited with interest.

P. B. S.

SIR P. C. RAY SEVENTIETH BIRTHDAY

COMMEMORATION MEDAL

Applications are invited for the above medal from young Indian Chemists below thirty years of age for the best single original contribution published in the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society during 1934. The relevant rules are given below.

The award for 1933 has been made in favour of Mr. S. K. Ray for his work on "Studies on Polyhalides."

P. RAY,
Hony. Secretary,
Indian Chemical Society.

RULES

1. The medal will be awarded annually for the best original paper (single and not joint) on any subject in Chemistry published in the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society only.

2. The competition for the medal shall be open to candidates whose age must not exceed thirty.

3. The candidates for the prize shall be required to submit an age certificate or corroboration of the same, confirmed by the Head of the department where they have worked.

4. The candidates, when communicating for publication in the Society's Journal, the paper intended for competition, must clearly make a statement to that effect.

5. The candidates for the medal shall submit their application not later than 31st October in every year, stating the title of their papers and the issue of the Journal in which they have been published.

6. No paper, which was submitted or has already been submitted for any other prizes or any examination, other than the M.A. or M.Sc. examination of the Indian Universities will be accepted for the present competition.

7. The merits of the papers shall be judged either by the Council of the Society or by the Board of Examiners, appointed by it, whose decision shall be considered final.
